

Clinical Presentation and Management of Gall Bladder Cancer – An Observational StudyYusuf Bhalawala¹, Sujoy Mukherjee², Arjun Agarwal³, Vijender Kumar⁴¹Resident, Department of General surgery at Rohilkhand Medical College and Hospital, Bareilly, Uttar Pradesh²Professor, Department of General surgery at Rohilkhand Medical College and Hospital, Bareilly, Uttar Pradesh³Associate professor, Department of General surgery (Oncosurgeon) at Rohilkhand Medical College and Hospital, Bareilly, Uttar Pradesh⁴Assistant professor, Department of General surgery at Rohilkhand Medical College and Hospital, Bareilly, Uttar Pradesh

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Introduction: Gallbladder cancer (GBC) is highly prevalent in India with an incidence rate of 1.8 per 100,000, contributing to cancer-related deaths globally. Late diagnosis, attributed to absence of reliable screening tests, results in advanced stages and poor prognosis. Symptoms vary asymptomatic to pain, jaundice and GI discomfort. Most commonly asso. Gallstones, GBC often presents late. Despite being the 19th most diagnosed cancer, it ranks 15th in India for mortality. This study aims to highlight key aspects including Clinical features, risk factors, pathogenesis, imaging characteristics & emphasizing early detection and comprehensive management approaches tailored to staging.

Aim: To study clinical presentation and management modalities of gall bladder cancer.

Methods: The study was conducted on 170 patients, patient data was collected on admission and diagnosis was made using clinical presentation and radiological investigation and analysed for early detection of clinical presentation of GBC and management planned and follow up was done for survival result in study period.

Results: The study had the following findings

1. The proportion of Females having GBC was 60% (102 off 170) higher than Males (40%), ratio between the male and female patients was 0.6667: 1.
2. Median incidence of gall bladder cancer in this study occurred in 6th decade (51-60 years)
3. Pain in abdomen was commonest complain present in 66% of patients followed by Jaundice 62% and vomiting in 51% of patients in our study group
4. In our study we observed the most common stage observed were IIB and IIIA with 64(37.65%) and 60(35.29%) with personal habits, such as smoking, alcohol, and irregular bowel habits, were most commonly observed in particular stages of gallbladder cancer and CECT W/A was the main modality of investigation for diagnosis and metastasis of GBC in suspected patients.

Conclusions: This study identified key demographic trends, symptomatology, and treatment patterns. Patients typically presented with pain, jaundice, and vomiting, with pain most common clinical presentation. Disease staging showed associations with age, sex, and personal habits like smoking and alcohol use. Management as Palliative care was predominant in advanced stages and older patients, correlating with higher mortality rates. Early-stage patients undergoing surgery and adjuvant chemotherapy had better survival rates, contrasting with late-stage patients receiving palliative care and chemotherapy. This highlights the importance of early diagnosis, aggressive treatment, and tailored interventions for improved outcomes in gallbladder cancer.

Keywords: Gall Bladder Cancer (GBC), Clinical Profile, Management.

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Introduction

Gall bladder cancer (GBC) is a common malignancy of the gastrointestinal tract and is the most common malignancy of biliary tract cancer in India, having an age standardized incidence rate of 1.8 per 100,000 population. [1] It is one of the most

aggressive cancers affecting the biliary tract, characterized by the shortest median survival time from diagnosis. [2] Among individuals deemed eligible for resection, the intricate anatomy of the Porto-biliary hepatic system, the morbidity and

mortality linked with liver resection, and the potential risks of tumor dissemination due to tumor manipulation, all contribute to a considerable mortality rate. Furthermore, post-surgical resection, and recurrence rates remain significantly high. [2]

Despite its small anatomy, measuring only about one inch (2 cm) in width, gallbladder associated cancers contribute to a significant global health burden, resulting in approximately 165,000 cancer-related fatalities each year. This accounts for approximately 1.7% of all cancer-related deaths worldwide. [4] Maxmillan de Stol in 1777, first described gall bladder carcinoma and various studies have revealed a trend of GBC illness late diagnosis and inadequate therapy. [5] Gall bladder cancer often features vascular invasion, distant metastases, and metastasis in regional lymph node.

Incidence varies widely within the country of GBC [6] but Majority of cases are reported widely from the northern belt (The Ganges belt) and mainly from the countries centre regions, although from the south is hardly ever reported. [7]

Diagnosis when made, patients with GBC are typically asymptomatic or report symptoms including stomach discomfort, nausea or vomiting, indigestion, weakness, anorexia, loss of appetite, weight loss, and sometimes jaundice, which might be misdiagnosed as cholecystitis due to its ambiguous description. In 2012 Arunkumar et al in south india, did research with 38 men and 23 women (Male: Female ratio 1.6:1). The majority of patients (42%) who were seen had right upper quadrant discomfort, jaundice (27%), and a palpable lump (12 percent). Abdominal ultrasonography and CECT abdomen allowed for the pre-operative diagnosis of GBC. [8]

As per GLOBOCAN 2022 statistics, gallbladder cancer ranks as the 19th most commonly diagnosed cancer in India, yet it stands as the 15th deadliest in India according to death rate. The disproportionately high fatality rate associated with gallbladder cancer is primarily due to its infrequent early detection [9]

This study contributes to the current body of literature on gallbladder cancer, aiming to raise awareness of early clinical detection of this relatively rare yet potentially treatable disease. We observed an overview of key aspects including Clinical features, risk factors, pathogenesis, imaging characteristics, and management of gall bladder cancer along with prognosis of gallbladder cancer. Special attention is given to the clinical presentation and management modalities according to staging of patients of gallbladder cancer.

Aim:

- To study clinical presentation and management modalities of gall bladder cancer.
- Objectives:
- To identify patterns of clinical presentation of gall bladder cancer in this region and management modalities of gall bladder cancer.

Material and Methods

Place of Study: The Present study was conducted in Department of General surgery at Rohilkhand Medical College and Hospital, Bareilly, Uttar Pradesh.

Type of Study: Observational study

Study duration: 1 year- 1 November 2022 to 31ST October 2023.

Subject: The Patients that presented with clinical features of gall bladder cancer with investigation suggesting of gall bladder cancer were considered for this study.

Sample Size: A sample size of 170 was calculated using the formula $4pq/L^2$

Inclusion Criteria: Patients presenting with all clinical features of gall bladder cancer and have investigation indicating of gall bladder cancer.

Exclusion Criteria: All the Patients with suspected Carcinoma Gall Bladder, which were later found out to be Benign Intarepithelial Neoplasia / Cholecystitis after radical cholecystectomy.

Methodology: All patients of Gall bladder cancer who fulfilled the Objectives with Inclusion and Exclusion criteria were admitted in the surgical ward of the Department of general surgery at Rohilkhand Medical College and hospital during 1 November 2022 to 31ST October 2023 were enrolled in this study. This is a study of factors commonly responsible for characteristics presentation of Gall Bladder cancer and determination of early diagnosis of GBC and management of gall bladder cancer in this region.

Operative Management: Radical Cholecystectomy

Palliative Management: PTBD (Percutaneous Transhepatic Biliary Drainage)

Conservative Management: Chemotherapy drugs were started in patients with advance cancer stage and most common regime used was inj. Cisplatin (day 1/ day 8) + inj. Gemcitabine (day 1/ day 8) + inj. Filgrastin 300mg s/c (on day 2) was given every 3 weekly.

A detailed clinical history and clinical examination was done in all cases presenting with clinical features of gall bladder cancer. The initial investigations done was USG (WHOLE ABDOMEN). CECT whole abdomen

(investigation was done to confirm staging), PET-CT (investigation was done to confirm metastasis and advanced disease).

The diagnosis confirmed on CECT (investigation done to confirm staging), PET-CT (investigation done to confirm metastasis and advanced disease) and Laparoscopic Biopsy for metastatic changes. After confirmation of diagnosis preoperative

procedural investigations like Hb%, TLC, DLC, Blood urea Serum creatinine, Liver function test, ECG, Chest X-ray and viral markers was done. Procedure was chosen among Radical cholecystectomy, open cholecystectomy, PTBD or conservative management or palliative care for advance disease.

Observations:

Table 1: Distribution of age and socioeconomic status w.r.t Sex, N = 170

Variable	Female, N = 102 (60%) ¹	Male, N = 68 (40%) ¹	Total, N = 170 ¹
Age (in years)			
Mean \pm SD	51 \pm 11	52 \pm 14	51 \pm 13
Median (IQR)	50 (42, 60)	53 (42, 60)	51 (42, 60)
Range	25, 81	14, 77	14, 81
Age (Categorical)			
10 - 20	0 (0%)	3 (4.4%)	3 (1.8%)
21 - 30	1 (1.0%)	1 (1.5%)	2 (1.2%)
31 - 40	21 (21%)	11 (16%)	32 (19%)
41 - 50	32 (31%)	15 (22%)	47 (28%)
51 - 60	29 (28%)	23 (34%)	52 (31%)
61 - 70	13 (13%)	11 (16%)	24 (14%)
> 70	6 (5.9%)	4 (5.9%)	10 (5.9%)
Socio-Economic Status			
APL	40 (39%)	21 (31%)	61 (36%)
BPL	62 (61%)	47 (69%)	109 (64%)
¹ n (%)			

Table 1 shows the distribution of age and socio-economic status. Where overall median age of participants (Gall bladder cancer patients) was 51 yrs with IQR of 42 – 60. Males had higher median age rather than females. Most (31%) of the participants belong to 51 – 60 years age category.

Maximum proportion within female population (31%) was in 41 – 50 years while maximum proportion of males were from 51 – 60 years. Overall 64% of the participants were BPL (Below poverty line) and Male had higher BPL (69%) participants rather than female (61%).

Table 2: Distribution of symptoms presenting at Outpatient clinic corresponding to sex; N = 170

Variable	Female, N = 102 (60%) ¹	Male, N = 68 (40%) ¹	Total, N = 170 ¹
Pain			
Yes	72 (71%)	41 (60%)	113 (66%)
No	30 (29%)	27 (40%)	57 (34%)
Generalized weakness / fever			
Yes	28 (27%)	27 (40%)	55 (32%)
No	74 (73%)	41 (60%)	115 (68%)
Vomiting			
Yes	51 (50%)	36 (53%)	87 (51%)
No	51 (50%)	32 (47%)	83 (49%)
Loss of weight			
Yes	24 (24%)	20 (29%)	44 (26%)
No	78 (76%)	48 (71%)	126 (74%)
Unknown swelling			
Yes	1 (1.0%)	1 (1.5%)	2 (1.2%)
No	101 (99%)	67 (99%)	168 (99%)
¹ n (%)			

Table 2 shows the distribution of presenting symptoms of the patients with respect to sex. Overall, most common symptoms which was seen in the participants was pain (66%) while least

common was unknown swelling (1.2%). Pain was seen in 71% of the females and 60% of the males. Generalised weakness or fever were seen in 40% of the males while only 27% of the females. Vomiting

was seen almost equally in both the sexes. Loss of weight was seen more commonly (29%) in male

participants while in female participants it was only 24%.

Table 3: Distribution of signs examined at Outpatient clinic within patients of Gall bladder cancer corresponding to sex; N = 170

Variable	Female, N = 102 (60%) ¹	Male, N = 68 (40%) ¹	Total, N = 170 ¹
Jaundice			
Yes	58 (57%)	47 (69%)	105 (62%)
No	44 (43%)	21 (31%)	65 (38%)
Abdominal distention			
Yes	19 (19%)	18 (26%)	37 (22%)
No	83 (81%)	50 (74%)	133 (78%)
Palpable lump			
Yes	14 (14%)	9 (13%)	23 (14%)
No	88 (86%)	59 (87%)	147 (86%)

Table 3 shows the presence and absence of the findings of technical examination with respect to sex of the gall bladder cancer patients. Overall, most common clinical finding was jaundice at 62% while least common was palpable lump at 14%. In

female gallbladder cancer patients 57% had jaundice, 19% had abdominal distention and 14% had a palpable lump. In males 69% of the participant had jaundice, 26% had abdominal distention and 13% had palpable lump.

Figure 1:

Figure 2:

Table 4: Distribution of Age and sex as per the staging of gall bladder cancer; N= 170

Types	IIA, N = 16 (9.41%) ¹	IIB, N = 64 (37.65%) ¹	IIIA, N = 60 (35.29%) ¹	IIIB, N = 7 (4.12%) ¹	IVA, N = 16 (9.41%) ¹	IVB, N = 7 (4.12%) ¹	Total, N = 170 ¹	p-value ²
Age (in years)								0.04
Mean ± SD	55 ± 12	48 ± 14	53 ± 11	59 ± 13	54 ± 11	49 ± 8	51 ± 13	
Median (IQR)	59 (48, 61)	50 (38, 55)	51 (43, 60)	60 (55, 67)	53 (45, 62)	48 (43, 54)	51 (42, 60)	
Range	31, 77	14, 81	28, 77	35, 75	35, 80	40, 60	14, 81	
Sex								0.035
Female	11 (69%)	47 (73%)	32 (53%)	3 (43%)	6 (38%)	3 (43%)	102 (60%)	
Male	5 (31%)	17 (27%)	28 (47%)	4 (57%)	10 (63%)	4 (57%)	68 (40%)	

¹n (%), ²Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test; Fisher's exact test

Table 4 shows the tabular representation of age and sex with respect to stage of gall bladder cancer. Highest proportion (73%) of the patient belongs to IIB (37.65%) and IIIA (35.29%) stage of gall bladder cancer. Highest median 60 with IQR (55, 67) age was seen in stage IIIB while lowest median 50 with IQR (38, 55) age was seen in stage IIB. Age

distribution was statistically significant (< 0.05) with respect to stages of gall bladder cancer using Kruskal Wallis rank sum test. Within females most common presenting stage was IIB at 46% and within mails it was IIIA at 41%. Sex distribution was statistically significant (<0.05) with stage of gallbladder cancer using Fisher's exact test.

Figure 3: Box and Violin showing age distribution w.r.t stage of gall bladder cancer; N = 170

Figure 3 shows the box and violin plot visualising stages of gall bladder cancer attack axis and age at y axis. Kruskal Wallis rank sum test revealed that, across 170 participants overall age distribution was statistically significant with stages of gall bladder

cancer at 0.04 p value. The effect size was 0.07 (0.03, 1) was low, as per Cohen’s (1988) conventions. Using Bonferroni corrections, we found that none of the pairwise distribution were statistically significant.

Table 5: Distribution of Personal characteristics corresponding to staging of gall bladder cancer; N= 170

Types	IIA, N = 16 (9.41%) ¹	IIB, N = 64 (37.65%) ¹	IIIA, N = 60 (35.29%) ¹	IIIB, N = 7 (4.12%) ¹	IVA, N = 16 (9.41%) ¹	IVB, N = 7 (4.12%) ¹	Total, N = 170 ¹	p-value ²
Smoking								<0.001
Yes	3.00 (18.75%)	11.00 (17.19%)	25.00 (41.67%)	4.00 (57.14%)	10.00 (62.50%)	4.00 (57.14%)	57.00 (33.53%)	
No	13.00 (81.25%)	53.00 (82.81%)	35.00 (58.33%)	3.00 (42.86%)	6.00 (37.50%)	3.00 (42.86%)	113.00 (66.47%)	
Tobacco								0.6
Yes	1.00 (6.25%)	5.00 (7.81%)	8.00 (13.33%)	1.00 (14.29%)	3.00 (18.75%)	1.00 (14.29%)	19.00 (11.18%)	
No	15.00 (93.75%)	59.00 (92.19%)	52.00 (86.67%)	6.00 (85.71%)	13.00 (81.25%)	6.00 (85.71%)	151.00 (88.82%)	
Alcohol								0.011
Yes	3.00 (18.75%)	6.00 (9.38%)	18.00 (30.00%)	3.00 (42.86%)	5.00 (31.25%)	3.00 (42.86%)	38.00 (22.35%)	
No	13.00 (81.25%)	58.00 (90.63%)	42.00 (70.00%)	4.00 (57.14%)	11.00 (68.75%)	4.00 (57.14%)	132.00 (77.65%)	
Bowel Habits								<0.001
Irregular	11.00 (68.75%)	30.00 (46.88%)	51.00 (85.00%)	7.00 (100.00%)	14.00 (87.50%)	5.00 (71.43%)	118.00 (69.41%)	
Regular	5.00 (31.25%)	34.00 (53.13%)	9.00 (15.00%)	0.00 (0.00%)	2.00 (12.50%)	2.00 (28.57%)	52.00 (30.59%)	

¹n (%),²Fisher's exact test

Table 5 shows the tabular representation of age and sex with respect to stage of gall bladder cancer. Considering IIIB to IVB proportion of participants who smoke was higher than the participants who did not smoke Alcohol intake was

seen most seen in stage IIIA (18 out of 38). Smoking, Alcohol Intake and Bowel habits had statistically significant association (p-value: < 0.001, 0.011 and < 0.001 respectively) with stages of gall bladder cancer

Figure 4: Stacked Bar plot showing distribution of Alcohol (A), Smoking (B) and Tobacco (C) usage corresponding to staging of Gall bladder cancer; N = 170

Figure 4 presents three stacked bar graphs (A, B, C) depicting the prevalence of alcohol consumption, smoking, and tobacco use among gall bladder cancer patients across stages IIA to IVB. Graph A shows a low prevalence of alcohol

consumption in early stages (IIA, IIB), increasing in later stages. Graph B indicates a similar trend for smoking, with a significant increase in stage IVA. Graph C reveals consistently low tobacco use across all stages.

Table 6: Distribution of symptoms presenting at Outpatient clinic corresponding to stages of Gall bladder Cancer; N = 170

Types	IIA, N = 16 (9.41%) ¹	IIB, N = 64 (37.65%) ¹	IIIA, N = 60 (35.29%) ¹	IIIB, N = 7 (4.12%) ¹	IVA, N = 16 (9.41%) ¹	IVB, N = 7 (4.12%) ¹	Total, N = 170 ¹	p-value ²
Pain								0.2
Yes	14.00 (87.50%)	46.00 (71.88%)	36.00 (60.00%)	4.00 (57.14%)	10.00 (62.50%)	3.00 (42.86%)	113.00 (66.47%)	
No	2.00 (12.50%)	18.00 (28.13%)	24.00 (40.00%)	3.00 (42.86%)	6.00 (37.50%)	4.00 (57.14%)	57.00 (33.53%)	
Generalized weakness / fever								0.14
Yes	4.00 (25.00%)	14.00 (21.88%)	24.00 (40.00%)	3.00 (42.86%)	6.00 (37.50%)	4.00 (57.14%)	55.00 (32.35%)	
No	12.00 (75.00%)	50.00 (78.13%)	36.00 (60.00%)	4.00 (57.14%)	10.00 (62.50%)	3.00 (42.86%)	115.00 (67.65%)	
Vomiting								>0.9
Yes	8.00 (50.00%)	32.00 (50.00%)	32.00 (53.33%)	3.00 (42.86%)	8.00 (50.00%)	4.00 (57.14%)	87.00 (51.18%)	
No	8.00 (50.00%)	32.00 (50.00%)	28.00 (46.67%)	4.00 (57.14%)	8.00 (50.00%)	3.00 (42.86%)	83.00 (48.82%)	
Loss of weight								0.054
Yes	2.00 (12.50%)	11.00 (17.19%)	18.00 (30.00%)	3.00 (42.86%)	6.00 (37.50%)	4.00 (57.14%)	44.00 (25.88%)	
No	14.00 (87.50%)	53.00 (82.81%)	42.00 (70.00%)	4.00 (57.14%)	10.00 (62.50%)	3.00 (42.86%)	126.00 (74.12%)	
Unknown swelling								0.054
Yes	0.00 (0.00%)	0.00 (0.00%)	0.00 (0.00%)	0.00 (0.00%)	2.00 (12.50%)	0.00 (0.00%)	2.00 (1.18%)	
No	16.00 (100.00%)	64.00 (100.00%)	60.00 (100.00%)	7.00 (100.00%)	14.00 (87.50%)	7.00 (100.00%)	168.00 (98.82%)	

¹n (%),²Fisher's exact test

Table 6 shows distribution of presence and absence of symptoms presenting with respect to stages of gall bladder cancer.

Pain showed decreasing trend of prevalence from stage IIA (87.5%) to stage IVB (42.86%) with mild increase from stage III to IVA (57.14% to 62.50%).

Aside from stage IVB presence of pain was higher in other stages as compared to absence of pain. Pain was seen most commonly in stage IIB patients (46 out of 13).

Regarding generalised weakness or fever, it was seen most commonly in stage IIIA (24 out of 55).

Table 7: Distribution of Signs presenting at Outpatient clinic corresponding to stages of Gall bladder Cancer; N = 170

Types	IIA, N = 16 (9.41%) ¹	IIB, N = 64 (37.65%) ¹	IIIA, N = 60 (35.29%) ¹	IIIB, N = 7 (4.12%) ¹	IVA, N = 16 (9.41%) ¹	IVB, N = 7 (4.12%) ¹	Total, N = 170 ¹	p-value ²
Jaundice								0.3
Yes	8.00 (50.00%)	34.00 (53.13%)	41.00 (68.33%)	5.00 (71.43%)	12.00 (75.00%)	5.00 (71.43%)	105.00 (61.76%)	
No	8.00 (50.00%)	30.00 (46.88%)	19.00 (31.67%)	2.00 (28.57%)	4.00 (25.00%)	2.00 (28.57%)	65.00 (38.24%)	
Abdominal distention								0.050
Yes	1.00 (6.25%)	9.00 (14.06%)	17.00 (28.33%)	3.00 (42.86%)	6.00 (37.50%)	1.00 (14.29%)	37.00 (21.76%)	
No	15.00 (93.75%)	55.00 (85.94%)	43.00 (71.67%)	4.00 (57.14%)	10.00 (62.50%)	6.00 (85.71%)	133.00 (78.24%)	
Palpable lump								0.2
Yes	1.00 (6.25%)	6.00 (9.38%)	10.00 (16.67%)	1.00 (14.29%)	2.00 (12.50%)	3.00 (42.86%)	23.00 (13.53%)	
No	15.00 (93.75%)	58.00 (90.63%)	50.00 (83.33%)	6.00 (85.71%)	14.00 (87.50%)	4.00 (57.14%)	147.00 (86.47%)	

¹n (%),²Fisher's exact test

Table 7 shows distribution of presence and absence of findings after clinical examination with respect to stages of gall bladder cancer. Jaundice showed increasing trend of prevalence from stage IIA (50%) to stage IVA (75%) while slight decrease from IVA to IVB (71.43%). Regarding abdominal

distension there was an increasing trend from IIA (6.25%) to IIIB (42.86%) while there was a decreasing trend from IIIB to IVB (14.29%). None of the clinical examination findings were found to have significant association with stages of gall bladder cancer. (p value ≥ 0.05).

Figure 5: Box and Violin plot showing distribution of age w.r.t management of Gall bladder carcinoma; N = 170

Fig 5 shows that people who had only palliative care were having higher median age (60) while lower median age patients (48) were selected for operative management. Age had statistically signif-

icant association with type of management. Post hoc adjustment with holmer found that pairwise distribution was significant between conservative and palliative care & operative and palliative care.

Table 8: Distribution of deaths within patients w.r.t investigations, Staging and management; N = 170

Types	Yes, N = 43 (25.29%) ¹	No, N = 127 (74.71%) ¹	Total, N = 170 ¹	p-value ²
Investigation				<0.001
CECT	21.00 (48.84%)	81.00 (63.78%)	102.00 (60.00%)	
PET-CT	21.00 (48.84%)	15.00 (11.81%)	36.00 (21.18%)	
USG	1.00 (2.33%)	31.00 (24.41%)	32.00 (18.82%)	
Staging of gall bladder cancer				<0.001
IIA	0.00 (0.00%)	16.00 (12.60%)	16.00 (9.41%)	
IIB	6.00 (13.95%)	58.00 (45.67%)	64.00 (37.65%)	
IIIA	23.00 (53.49%)	37.00 (29.13%)	60.00 (35.29%)	
IIIB	4.00 (9.30%)	3.00 (2.36%)	7.00 (4.12%)	
IVA	8.00 (18.60%)	8.00 (6.30%)	16.00 (9.41%)	
IVB	2.00 (4.65%)	5.00 (3.94%)	7.00 (4.12%)	
Management				<0.001
Conservative	16.00 (37.21%)	80.00 (62.99%)	96.00 (56.47%)	
Operative	4.00 (9.30%)	37.00 (29.13%)	41.00 (24.12%)	
Palliative Care	23.00 (53.49%)	10.00 (7.87%)	33.00 (19.41%)	

¹n (%), ²Pearson's Chi-squared test; Fisher's exact test

Discussion

Gallbladder cancer (GBC) is a highly lethal disease with a poor prognosis, primarily due to late-stage diagnosis. The survival rate for advanced GBC is dismal, with median survival ranging from 5% to 10%. Most patients are diagnosed at an advanced stage when symptoms, such as abdominal pain and jaundice, have already manifested. Distinguishing GBC symptoms from those of gallstone disease is challenging, and most tumors are unrespectable at diagnosis. Consequently, the focus of treatment for many patients shifts to palliative care, aimed at alleviating symptoms like pain, jaundice, and vomiting. Endoscopic palliative treatments have been increasingly used to improve quality of life by addressing issues such as obstructive jaundice.

In this study, the highest incidence of GBC was observed in patients aged 51–60, with females making up nearly 60% of cases, aligning with previous research. Pain was the most common presenting symptom, followed by jaundice and vomiting. This matches findings from other studies, which also reported abdominal pain as a frequent symptom in GBC patients, especially in advanced cases. Female predominance was noted, with multiple studies reporting a higher incidence of GBC in women compared to men.

The incidence of GBC varies regionally within India, with higher rates in urban areas like Delhi. Studies show a rising trend in GBC cases across India over the last few decades, with the disease more prevalent among females than males. Lifestyle factors such as smoking, alcohol intake, and irregular bowel habits were commonly observed among GBC patients, particularly in stages IIB and IIIA. Addiction, advancing age, and irregular bowel habits were frequently associated with GBC.

In terms of diagnostic tools, ultrasound (USG) and computed tomography (CT) scans were commonly used to detect GBC. In this study, ultrasound revealed gallbladder wall thickening in a significant number of patients, while CT scans were more accurate in detecting advanced disease stages, such as liver involvement. Positron emission tomography (PET-CT) was used in patients with advanced GBC, showing good sensitivity in detecting metastases. Other studies confirmed the effectiveness of these imaging techniques, with CT having around 71% accuracy for staging GBC. Regarding treatment, radical cholecystectomy remains the primary surgical option for early-stage GBC, showing favorable outcomes in patients with

stage IIB cancer. In this study, 41 patients underwent surgery, with radical cholecystectomy being the most common procedure. For advanced stages, palliative care, including chemotherapy and procedures like percutaneous transhepatic biliary drainage (PTBD), was often recommended. Chemotherapy, particularly with gemcitabine and platinum-based regimens, has been the mainstay for treating unresectable and metastatic GBC. In this study, patients in advanced stages often received conservative management, including chemotherapy, with PTBD performed for those experiencing jaundice and biliary obstruction.

A notable finding from this study was the association between lifestyle habits and GBC progression. Smoking, alcohol consumption, and irregular bowel habits were prevalent in specific stages of the disease, particularly in older age groups. Smoking was more common in males, while irregular bowel habits were more frequently reported among females.

The mortality rate in GBC is high, especially in patients with advanced disease. In this study, out of 170 patients, 43 died during the follow-up period, most of whom had presented with jaundice, vomiting, and abdominal pain. The majority of these patients were in advanced stages when diagnosed, which significantly limited treatment options. Studies like GLOBOCAN 2018 reported that GBC mortality rates are higher in women than men, reflecting the gender disparity in incidence rates.

Neoadjuvant therapy is emerging as a potential treatment option for GBC, especially for patients with locally advanced unresectable disease. Studies have shown that neoadjuvant chemotherapy, such as the combination of gemcitabine and cisplatin (GC regimen), may improve outcomes by enabling surgery or enhancing prognosis in patients with resectable disease. The ongoing GAIN trial aims to assess the efficacy of neoadjuvant therapy in improving overall survival for GBC patients, with results expected in 2024. This could mark a significant shift in treatment paradigms for GBC, particularly for those with advanced disease.

In conclusion, GBC remains a challenging and deadly disease, with poor survival rates due to late-stage diagnosis. Surgery is the best option for early-stage GBC, while chemotherapy and palliative care are the main treatments for advanced stages. Emerging therapies like neoadjuvant treatment offer hope for improving outcomes in the future.

Figure 6 S/O: Radical Cholecystectomy with En Bloc Segment IVb/V Hepatic Resection for Gallbladder Cancer

Conclusion

Our study concluded that patients who presented early with clinical symptoms and investigations indicative of gallbladder cancer (GBC) and were in early stage had surgical treatment and adjuvant chemotherapy had a higher survival rate and fewer postoperative complications during the study period.

In addition, patients who presented late with advanced stage of cancer and received palliative care along with chemotherapy treatment had a better survival outcome than those who received only palliative care alone.

This study provides various insights into determining the clinical presentations for early GBC diagnosis, the most effective investigation to diagnose GBC at early stage, and the therapeutic management modalities for patients presenting at various clinical stages.

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